

PERSONALITY TRAITS OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

R. Azhagu Ganesan* & Dr. R. Annadurai**

* Research Scholar, Centre for Educational Research, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai, Tamilnadu

** Director i/c, Centre for Educational Research, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: R. Azhagu Ganesan & Dr. R. Annadurai, "Personality Traits of Higher Secondary Students", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 379-382, 2018.

Abstract:

Personality refers to the total quality of a person – it refers to the unique way he adjusts himself to the outside world. It covers the physical, intellectual, emotional and social aspects of the individually. Personality gains meaning only in social situations. There are two major approaches to assessment of personality – trait approach and holistic approach. In holistic approach one's personality is assessed as a 'whole'. Personality is operationally defined as constituting several fairly consistent traits which are identified and the individuals are assessed in each of the traits. The individual can identify his plus points and minus points. He can make the best use of his plus points and employ measures of rectifying his minus points.

Key Words: Personality Traits and Higher Secondary Students

Need for the Study:

Personality psychology concerns what our personalities are, how they work, and what they can mean to our own and others' futures. The trait approach to personality is one of the major theoretical areas in the study of personality. The trait theory suggests that individual personalities are composed broad dispositions. Consider how we would describe the personality of a close friend. Chances are that we would list a number of traits, such as outgoing, kind and even-tempered. A trait can be thought of as a relatively stable characteristic that causes individuals to behave in certain ways.

Unlike many other theories of personality, such as psychoanalytic or humanistic theories, the trait approach to personality is focused on differences between the individuals. The combination and interaction of various traits forms a personality that is unique to each individual. Trait theory is focused on identifying and measuring these individual personality characteristics. But not many more systematic and scientific attempt is found made on the measurement of personality traits among students, in general and college students in particular till date. So the present study intends to measure to personality traits which is entitled the present study, "Personality Traits of Higher Secondary Students in Madurai District".

Terms and Definitions:

- Personality traits - refer to the distinguishing quality or characteristic, as of personality of the higher secondary students.
- Higher secondary students: refers to those who are studying XI and XII standard in Madurai district.

Variables of the Study:

Dependent Variable:

- Personality Traits

Independent Variables:

- Gender : Male/ Female
- Subject : Arts/Science
- School Locality : Urban/Rural
- School Kind : Unisex/Mixed

Objectives of the Study:

Following are the specific objectives framed for the study:

- To measure the level of personality traits of higher secondary students.
- To find out the significant influence of independent variables viz., Gender, Subject, School locality

Hypotheses of the Study:

The following hypotheses are formulated in the present study:

- Personality traits of higher secondary students is above the average level.
- Gender exerts a significant influence on personality traits of higher secondary students.
- Subject exerts a significant influence on personality traits of higher secondary students.
- School locality exerts a significant influence on personality traits of higher secondary students.
- School kind exerts a significant influence on personality traits of higher secondary students.

Methodology-In-Brief:

Sample of the Study:

A stratified representative sample of 350 higher secondary students constituted from schools recognized by the Department of School Education, Tamil Nadu situated in Madurai District with due representation given to the variables viz., Gender, Subject, School locality, School kind.

Tools Used:

The following tools were used by the investigator for the data collection:

- General Information Sheet developed by the Investigator.
- Personality traits Scale developed by Sathyagirajan, S (2001).

Statistical Treatments:

The statistical treatments employed in the study are listed below:

- Mean
- Standard Deviation
- ‘t’- test for significance of difference between the means of large independent samples.
- Correlation Analysis – Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation-‘r’

Related Studies:

Cela-Ranilla, Jose Maria; Gisbert, Merce; de Oliveira, Janaina Minelli (2011) did a study on “Exploring the Relationship among Learning Patterns, Personality Traits, and Academic Performance in Freshmen”

Providing information about how 1st-year students learn may help colleges plan actions aimed at increasing students' persistence in higher education programs. This research aims to assess 1st-year students' academic performance, using a path analysis to establish inter-correlations among students' personality traits, learning patterns, high school achievement, and objectively measured outcomes. Participants included 509 freshmen from different academic disciplines. Results show a causality relations model in which Conscientiousness positively influences Sequential and Precise learning patterns as well as academic performance. The path model also confirms Extraversion as a negative antecedent of the Technical learning pattern. It is argued that knowing students is a primary step to putting them in a position to become an active part of the learning process

Hong, Zuway-R.; Lin, Huann-shyang (2011) did a study on “An Investigation of Students' Personality Traits and Attitudes toward Science”

The purposes of this study were to validate an instrument of attitudes toward science and to investigate grade level, type of school, and gender differences in Taiwan's students' personality traits and attitudes toward science as well as predictors of attitudes toward science. Nine hundred and twenty-two elementary students and 1,954 secondary students completed the School Student Questionnaire in 2008. Factor analyses, correlation analyses, ANOVAs, and regressions were used to compare the similarities and differences among male and female students in different grade levels. The findings were as follows: female students had higher interest in science and made more contributions in teams than their male counterparts across all grade levels. As students advanced through school, student scores on the personality trait scales of Conscientiousness and Openness sharply declined; students' scores on Neuroticism dramatically increased. Elementary school and academic high school students had significantly higher total scores on interest in science than those of vocational high and junior high school students. Scores on the scales measuring the traits of Agreeableness, Extraversion, and Conscientiousness were the most significant predictors of students' attitudes toward science. Implications of these findings for classroom instruction are discussed.

Hypotheses Verification:

Hypothesis 1: Personality traits among higher secondary students is above average

The average score of the Personality traits among higher secondary students is found to be 212, while the theoretical average is 144. This shows that the Personality traits among higher secondary students is above the average level. Hence the hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: Gender exerts a significant influence on personality traits among higher secondary students.

Table 1: Statistical measures and results of test of significance of difference between the means score of personality traits among higher secondary students: Gender-Wise

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	‘t’- value	Significance at 0.05 level
Gender	Male	181	211.64	48.82	-2.385	Significant
	Female	169	218.62	45.45		

It is evident from table 4.1, that the obtained ‘t’ value -2.385 is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between the male and female students in terms of personality traits among higher secondary students. Further, it is observed that female students have more personality traits than male students. Hence the hypothesis 2 is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: Subject exerts a significant influence on personality traits among higher secondary students.

Table 2: Statistical measures and results of test of significance of difference between the means score of personality traits among higher secondary students: Subject -Wise

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	' t'- value	Significance at 0.05 level
Subject	Arts	226	214.07	47.38	-0.499	Not Significant
	Science	124	216.71	47.25		

It is evident from table 4.2, that the obtained 't' value -0.499 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between the arts and science students in terms of personality traits among higher secondary students. Further, it is observed that Subject does not influence on personality traits among the students. Hence the hypothesis 3 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4: School locality exerts a significant influence on personality traits among higher secondary students.

Table 3: Statistical measures and results of test of significance of difference between the means score of personality traits among higher secondary students: School locality - Wise

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	' t'- value	Significance at 0.05 level
School locality	Urban	131	216.46	43.34	0.459	Not Significant
	Rural	219	214.14	49.56		

It is evident from table 4.3, that the obtained 't' value 0.459 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between the urban and rural school students in terms of personality traits among higher secondary students. Further, it is observed that School locality does not influence on personality traits among the students. Hence the hypothesis 4 is rejected.

Hypothesis 5: School kind exerts a significant influence on personality traits among higher secondary students.

Table 4: Statistical measures and results of test of significance of difference between the means score of personality traits among higher secondary students: School kind -Wise

Variable	Sub-category	N	M	S.D	' t'- value	Significance at 0.05 level
School kind	Unisex	116	212.54	47.58	-0.666	Not Significant
	Mixed	148	216.45	47.10		

It is evident from table 4.4, that the obtained 't' value -0.666 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between the unisex and mixed school students in terms of personality traits among higher secondary students. Further, it is observed that School kind does not influence on personality traits among the students. Hence the hypothesis 5 is rejected.

Conclusions:

The major conclusions arrived at from the study are listed below:

- Personality traits among the higher secondary students is found high.
- Personality traits among the higher secondary students is found dependent upon-Gender
- Personality traits among the higher secondary students is found independent upon-
 - Subject
 - School locality
 - School kind

Educational Implications:

Personality trait makes a person as a whole man. Collective traits build the personality of the people good or bad. From this study twelve personality traits which may present in all persons but with different degrees, because each individual is differ from other individual. For example a person with higher self-confidence may get job advancement quickly and reach the top most rank, reverse is noticed in the person with lower self-confidence. Positive attitude towards life and self is present in the person/individual, he succeeds the life at the minimum age, time negative effect is noticed in the person/individual with negative attitudes of life and self. Thus personality trait may fix the ups and downs of the individual. Person with balanced personality traits achieve the life and it has both adverse as well as diverse effect on the achievement of the individual.

Many more programme like special lecture, camp activities related to personality development, counseling with help of psychologist may be arranged for higher secondary students to develop their personality.

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